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DETERMINING THE KNOWLEDGE LEVEL OF PUPILS IN THE "SMART SCHOOL" INFORMATION SYSTEM

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Abstract-At a time when current information technologies are rapidly developing, the effectiveness of the quality of education in general secondary schools, the transparency of the teacher evaluation system, and the analysis of several other indicators with the help of artificial intelligence are the current issues of the day. In this method of analysis, the value is initially entered by school experts.

Keywords. Smart school, information system, mathematical model, array, set elements, signs of similarity, association rule, time series, fuzzy logic.

Population growth in Uzbekistan leads to an increase in the number of pupils in schools, which increases the difference in the ratio of school teachers to pupils. Naturally, the teacher cannot always participate in the evaluation of the pupils' knowledge level, in determining the topics that are difficult to master, and in other processes related to education. The inability of teachers to deal with each pupil individually can lead to a sharp decrease in the quality of education.

Raising the quality of education in Uzbekistan to a higher level, raising the educational system to a higher level through the use of advanced information technologies, in particular, artificial intelligence, is considered one of the most important tasks today. Ensuring the intellectual and physical development of pupils

in schools, creating a foundation for them to fully use their abilities in the future and to find their place in society is one of the urgent issues of today [1].

The Smart School program is software designed for electronic management and analysis of work processes in schools, including journals and daily documents, and serves to automate the work of school director, deputies director, teachers and other employees. The system performs analysis of pupils' cognitive potential and physical development in the educational system using Artificial Intelligence systems (search based on associative rules, time series prediction, fuzzy logic).

Automation of the educational process in the higher and general secondary education system is one of the pain points of the education system [2][3]. At present, this problem has been partially solved, that is, an automated information system for secondary education has been developed. Currently, the system has been put into practice in 10 general public schools in Fergana city in Uzbekistan [4]. The "Smart School" program allows to analyze the effectiveness of the quality of education in schools, the transparency of the teacher evaluation system, and several other indicators with the help of artificial intelligence. In addition, subjects that are difficult for pupils in current schools to master are automatically identified. It is as a result of taking systematic measures on the topics that are difficult to master, identifying pupils who are inactive in classes and those with low mastery individually, effective work is being organized with each pupil. There are opportunities to regularly notify parents about changes in their child's learning in the form of a histogram in the mobile application, and to provide advice to teachers and parents in identifying pupils who regularly miss classes and finding the reasons for it.

Electronic journal, electronic diary, online information exchange with parents, ability to view exam schedule and results online, online lesson schedule will help pupils to fully participate in classes and improve learning efficiency [5]. It is also worth noting that the program has the ability to analyze the physical development and physical training of the pupil according to his age, to recommend physical exercises that should be performed according to the standard rules, and exercises to ensure the health of the pupil.

The large number of training load imposed on the teacher complicates the process of assessing the pupil's knowledge level. That is, if a teacher spends 3-7 minutes to assess the knowledge of 1 pupil through questions and answers, and there are 20-40 pupils in 1 class, it means that the teacher needs more time and

energy. Such problems can be solved through artificial intelligence systems. In the "Smart School" program, the grades received by the pupils in each subject are analyzed, and it is determined with the help of artificial intelligence systems which subjects the pupil is active in appropriation and which subjects there are problems[6].

Based on the mathematical models developed above and the business process modeled on their basis, a similarity detection function was introduced for the “Smart School” information system. 10 schools where the information system has been implemented are identifying pupils with a significant level of accuracy based on the information entered into the program. If this function is required to cover the grades of 10 school pupils, it is required to enter the resulting number of pupils. For example, the system needs to determine how many pupils have similar grades to the current pupil. In that case, the system requires the user to enter the required number of students. Apart from that, the system determined the indicators of learning in schools as follows:

1. Analyzing the learning of math by 10th grade pupils of schools 2, 21 and 40, it was found that learning the following topics was difficult for pupils (Table 1).

Table 1.

Schools	Themes		
	Negation, disjunction and conjunction	Simple percentage, complicated percentage	Simple rational equations and their systems
40 th school	4.18	3.18	3.82
21 st school	1.77	0.37	0.89
2 nd school	1.91	1.48	2.67

Table 1 shows that in 2 schools it is difficult for pupils of the 10th grade to master these topics in algebra, while in the 40th school, these topics are mastered relatively well. In this case, studying the methodology of the 40th school in teaching math and applying it to other schools can lead to the quality mastery of the subject in all schools.

2. In addition, the "Smart School" information system has the ability to determine the mastery coefficients of subjects that are difficult for pupils to master. This possibility can be seen in the diagram below:

It can be seen from the diagram that the coefficients of assimilation of subjects assessed as difficult to master within the framework of schools have been developed. In the system of public education, it is desirable to revise the methods of teaching these subjects in a more understandable form. In the same way, you can highlight topics that are more difficult to master in other subjects.

Summary. The developed information system identifies students with a high level of knowledge in accordance with such criteria as the number of grades received by students, the frequency of participation in classes, and indicators of mastery of subjects. For example, if we look at the example of the 10th school, it was found that there are 4 pupils in the 5th "A" class and 3 pupils with a high level of knowledge in the 6th "G" class. In addition, in the 10th school, the level of knowledge in the subject of the mother tongue of the 5th "E" grade was 4.9 on a maximum of 5 points, and the average indicator of the class was determined by the program according to the level of knowledge of each pupil. . Through this method of analysis, it will be possible to assess the level of knowledge of pupils and classes by school.

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